

**CONSULTING SERVICES FOR PROGRAMMING AND
IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MIP, TEIS AND JES (2021-2027)**

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Scoping Report

Date: 09/09/2022

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List of abbreviations

ADB	Asian Development Bank
AFD	French Development Agency
ASEAN	Association of Southeast Asian Nations
CDC	Council of Development for Cambodia
EBA	Everything but arms agreement
EIB	European Investment Bank
ESCR	Economic social and cultural rights
EU	European Union
EUD	EU Delegation to Cambodia
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment
FM / FMU	Forest Management / Forest Management Unit
GGGI	Global Green Growth Institute
GMAC	The Garment Manufacturers Association in Cambodia
GTF	Garment, Textile and Footwear
IDP	Industrial Development Policy
IESCR	The International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights
ILO	International Labour Organization
ITC	International Trade Centre
KfW	KfW Development Bank
LDC	Least Developed Countries
LoI	Law on Investment
LTS4CN	Long-Term Strategy For Carbon Neutrality 2050
MIP	Multi-Annual Indicative Programme
NGO	Non-Government Organisation
ODA	Official Development Assistance
RCEP	Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership
RGC	Royal Government of Cambodia
SEZ	Special Economic Zones
SME	Small & Medium Enterprises
SSC	Strategic Steering Committee
TEI	Team Europe Initiative
ToR	Terms of Reference
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNFCCC	the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

UNIDO	United Nations Industrial Development Organization
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
WB	World Bank

Scoping Assignment Objectives

- i. Provide a comprehensive sector review of Garment, Textile and Footwear (GTF) landscape in Cambodia, in the optic of what the EU and the Team Europe action in Cambodia.
- ii. Advise and finalise the TEI2 landscape (theory of change, log frame/indicator) and draft relevant parts of the SSC fiche (template with instruction provided in annexes).
- iii. Reflecting the EU added value and contribution in promoting environmental and social due diligence and gender- empowerment in the GTF industry.
- iv. The analysis will keep at its core the human element of the GTF sector in Cambodia, namely: decent employment, skills and the gender aspects, trying to make links with current and future involvement of TE in these aspects, within the GTF value-chain

Part 1

1. Context

1.1 EU Programming, MIP and Budget

The current EU budget cycle, known as the **Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) 2021-2027**, provides a streamlined approach towards international cooperation, known as ‘**Global Europe**’. This brings together EU policies on poverty reduction, protection of human rights and crisis response under a single instrument with **total funding of around EUR 79.4 billion** (CONCORD, 2022).

Figure 1: Global Europe funding allocation. Source: CONCORD (2022).

Global Europe is aligned to the Paris Agreement on Climate Change, allocating a spending target of 30 percent for climate action and biodiversity objectives to contribute 7.5 percent of annual MFF spending from 2024 and 10 percent from 2026. A key feature of the Global Europe instrument is “joint programming”, this is where the EU, its member states, development agencies and finance institutions agree to adopt a common multiannual programming framework for cooperation with partner countries.

Figure 2: overview of Team Europe working together on Joint Programming and Joint Implementation. Source: CONCORD (2022).

The Joint Programming, a common understanding of joint analysis, response and results, shared by Team Europe come together as Team Europe Initiative (TEIs), which can be either at country (up to two TEIs) or regional level and must link to priorities set in the Multiannual Indicative Programming (MIP).

EU programming over the period 2021 - 2027 has several important developments, the European External Action Service (EEAS) has brought together trade and sustainability issues, for instance, the legislative proposal for EU's General Scheme of Preferences (GSP) 2024 - 2034 aims to better respond to the evolving needs and challenges of GSP countries and reinforce the scheme's social, labour environmental and climate dimension (EEAS, 2021). In parallel the EU Action Plan on Human Rights and Democracy 2020 - 2024 is increasingly relevant to Cambodia given the recent partial suspension of Everything But Arms (EBA), an instrument of GSP (EC, 2020). Thus, the current programming cycle draws increasing attention to sustainability matters, all EU Laws are required to promote sustainable development, specifically with regards to social justice, respect to Human Rights, high labour standards and high environmental standards.

1.2 Team Europe Objectives

Team Europe Initiatives (TEI) is a coordinated effort to thematise and maximise cross-working priorities between EU member states, EIB, EBRD, and others. Currently, there are approximately 150 TEIs being prepared, sectorally, with each partner country expecting to

have at most two TEIs where majority of TEIs are climate related (Center for Global Development, 2021).

Currently, there are two initiatives proposed for Cambodia (EU, 2022):

1. **Natural Resources:** to promote sustainable use of natural resources, combining protection and increasing incomes for rural populations to support sustainable agriculture and agri-food value chains.
2. **Energy efficiency:** to move towards a more sustainable and inclusive diversification of the economy and integration with global and regional value chains. To promote energy efficiency, supporting clean energy and infrastructure, aimed at supporting sustainable and integrated export industry and value chains and contributing to trade facilitation measures and international market access.

1.3 EU Cambodia Cooperation

The current EU programming reflects an updated Joint European Strategy 2021-2027 (EEAS, 2022) which is the overarching strategic partnership between European partners in their development cooperation with Cambodia.

The Joint European Strategy 2021-2027 sets out six priority areas of mutual priorities between European and Cambodia partnership:

1. Strengthen democratic accountability
2. Foster democratic participation
3. Support quality, accessible and inclusive services to strengthen human development
4. Enhance competitiveness of Cambodia on the regional and global marketplaces
5. Sustainable green development
6. Active and coordinated support to the preservation of Cambodia's culture heritage

The Joint European Strategy is operationalised through programming in the EU-Cambodia Multi-annual Indicative Programme (MIP) 2021-2027 and responds to the COVID-19 pandemic. Under this framework, three priority areas have been identified for cooperation:

1. **Green growth and decent jobs**, aims at “greening for competitiveness”, with a specific focus on industrial value chains ensuring sustainable approach to natural resources and enhancing attention to climate change.
2. **Education and skills development**, strengthening skills to promote the private sector to create more and better jobs and economic growth.
3. **Good governance**, to improve better functioning of public financial management, rule of law, and a predicate trade and business climate.

1.4 Focal Sectors

The focal sectors between both EU and Cambodian priorities can be summarised in five key areas, as follows:

-
1. Energy
 2. Skills
 3. Labour
 4. Gender
 5. Market Access

1.4.1 Energy

Both EU and Cambodia have prioritised increase in capacity, reliability and cost effectiveness of clean energy. Clean energy is a high level strategic priority that significantly impacts all other priorities. Lack of continued supply of electricity and affordable energy is an impediment to the Garment, Textile and Footwear (GTF) sector as factories rely on consistent supply of power throughout the day. In 2019, there were increased demands for electricity due to droughts, thus, reducing output from hydropower, this was attributed to El Nino weather patterns (DW, 2019), on Aug 2022, Electricite du Cambodge (EDC) announced power outages as a result of a “damaged 230 kV high voltage diverter” (Khmer Times, 2022). During electricity outages, factories switch to diesel generators (ILO, 2015, p.10) which have a time lag and are more expensive to run. GGGI (2018a, p.21) estimate that diesel generated power costs an estimated USD 0.28/kWh, whereas, hydroelectric costs 0.075/kWh, coal at 0.0776/kWh and solar at 0.11/kWh (all USD), therefore, switching to diesel has significant costs to businesses.

Clean Energy can be met through better management of natural resources, increasing energy efficiency, and increasing the renewable energy mix. These are shared priorities between Cambodia and donors in country. Moreover, international buyers such as H&M have set climate targets providing strong market signal to invest more on clean energy infrastructure. Starting Jan 2022, there were to be no new suppliers onboarded with on-site coal boilers in their factories and within its own premises, H&M’s electricity use was 95% renewable (2021) as well entering into partnership with HSBC, WWF and World Resource Institute to allow Cambodia to be H&M’s first production country to use 100% biomass boilers (H&M, 2021, p.24).

1.4.2 Skills

The skills-level to operate effectively in the Garment, Textiles and Footwear (GTF) sector is low according to the latest strategy on Cambodia’s Garment, Footwear and Travel Goods (GFT¹) Sector Development Strategy 2022 – 2027 (National Supreme Economic Council, 2022, p.4) which is related to structural issues related to poor literacy. Whilst garment workers can operate in low-skilled roles, supervisors and managers are mostly foreign. The changing landscape of the GTF sector means there is an opportunity to align towards competitive skills relevant for Cambodia’s GTF sector and the international market. The Asian Development Bank’s (2021, p.4) report on the benefits of Industry 4.0 through skills development indicates Cambodia’s strategy to move up the GTF value chain will require enhanced knowledge of technologies and machinery related to Industry 4.0 and an increasing knowledge base of more sophisticated textile manufacturing. Moreover, with the changing competitive landscape, skills and knowledge will need to be aligned to standards such as

¹ This report will continue to use the Garment, Textiles and Footwear (GTF) sector whilst the sub sector strategy in Cambodia refers to it as GFT.

Occupation Safety and Health (OSH), technical and process innovations and global value chain knowledge building.

1.4.3 Labour

Over the past two decades, working conditions in the GTF sector have markedly improved, particularly in relation to basic occupational safety and health (OSH), setting out minimum wage and social security legislation, eliminating child labour and the expansion of social security benefits for workers (ILO, 2019c, p.10). Nevertheless, workers in the GTF sector still face serious decent work deficits including violations of trade union rights, poor industrial relations, low wages and a gender pay gap, abuse of fixed-term contracts, discrimination, violence and harassment, unsafe commutes and unprotected work in informal subcontracting factories. These issues prevent the GTF sector from being sustainable and hinder its competitiveness and reputation, thus, the ILO (2021, p.22) recommends Just Transition planning for policymakers, identifying and implementing policy mix for sustainable supply chains, enterprises and decent work.

1.4.4 Gender

Women make up 80 percent of the GTF sector in Cambodia (National Supreme Economic Council, 2022, p.i), whilst this is an opportunity to lift many women out of poverty, there are specific gendered issues to consider. The GTF sector reports systemic gender-based violence in the workplace and living neighbourhood, including high number of harassment either verbal or sexual (CARE International, 2017, p.5), women also bear the responsibility of family income, sending wages to their village and living on short budget (CARE International, 2017, p.46). Women are mostly found at the lower skilled level of working, poor literacy, restricted by limited knowledge of their rights as women, and as workers (CARE International, 2017, p.27). Factories low in gender policies and facilities, including on sexual and reproductive rights, contribute to high turn-over and absenteeism, and impact factories' productivity (CARE International, 2017, p.56).

1.4.5 Market access

In 2018, the GTF sector accounted for 74 percent of Cambodia's total merchandise exports, contributing significantly to foreign export earnings, underscoring the importance of global market access (ILO, 2019c, p.10). Currently, the US and EU are the largest export markets, however, Cambodia has also diversified exports to nearby Asian markets such as Japan (ILO, 2019a, p.3). Cambodia's Least Developed Countries (LDC) status gives preferential trade access and quotas which has enabled Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) flows to stimulate the GTF sector. Even when such an access was discontinued, the Multifiber Arrangement (MFA) with the US to give as an example, Cambodia was able to develop improved production models (National Supreme Economic Council, 2022, p.5). Market access has improved due to utilising several preferential trade agreements, alongside domestic market context such as investment laws, ease of doing business and supporting policies. However, the recent partial-suspension of the EUs Everything But Arms (EBA) signals increasing compliance of market access through standards and key global principles such as human rights and labour protection (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2019).

1.5 Budget

ODA disbursement to Cambodia 2020 - 2023: USD 6.8 billion

Overall, donor coordination of all countries into Cambodia between 2020 - 2023 indicates a total budget of USD 6.8 billion (European External Action Service, 2021, p.30). Out of the total planned Official Development Assistance (ODA), EU programming budget is USD 1.6 billion.

Cambodia - ODA disbursements 2020 and planned disbursements 2021-2023 by term of assistance (USD million)*									
Donor	Grant		Concessional Loan		Non-Concessional Loan		Total 2020	Total 2021-2023	Grand total
	2020 (disbursements)	2021-2023 (plans)	2020 (disbursements)	2021-2023 (plans)	2020 (disbursements)	2021-2023 (plans)			
Czech Republic	1.55	4.77	-	-	-	-	1.55	4.77	6.32
EU/EC	87.54	210.63	-	-	-	-	87.54	210.63	298.17
EIB	-	-	50.00	213.00	-	-	50.00	213.00	263.00
France	16.81	57.28	68.47	727.05	-	-	85.29	784.34	869.62
Germany	24.35	81.96	-	38.80	-	-	24.35	120.76	145.14
Ireland	1.17	0.72	-	-	-	-	1.17	0.72	1.90
Sweden	25.00	25.94	-	-	-	-	25.00	25.94	50.94
Sum EU**	156.43	381.32	118.47	978.86	-	-	274.90	1,360.18	1,635.09
Australia	30.53	53.59	-	-	-	-	30.53	53.59	84.12
Canada	1.54	2.55	-	-	-	-	1.54	2.55	4.08
China	93.51	117.88	363.50	423.82	6.13	2.18	463.14	543.88	1,007.02
Japan	99.61	159.26	475.50	824.16	-	-	575.11	983.42	1,558.53
New Zealand	5.74	9.21	-	-	-	-	5.74	9.21	14.94
Republic of Korea	27.06	79.52	17.55	281.31	-	-	44.61	360.83	405.44
Switzerland	15.57	27.28	-	-	-	-	15.57	27.28	42.85
UK	0.43	0.06	-	-	-	-	0.43	0.06	0.50
USA	96.39	180.07	-	-	-	-	96.39	180.07	276.46
Sum bilaterals	370.38	629.42	856.55	1,529.29	6.13	2.18	1,233.05	2,160.89	3,393.94
ADB	23.49	30.66	412.41	387.51	-	-	435.90	418.18	854.08
GAVI	8.87	9.11	-	-	-	-	8.87	9.11	17.98
Global Fund	39.70	101.72	-	-	-	-	39.70	101.72	141.42
World Bank	0.50	35.43	75.98	430.10	-	-	76.48	465.53	542.01
United Nations	47.91	136.54	9.60	50.46	0.00	0.73	57.51	187.72	245.24
Sum multilaterals	120.47	313.46	497.98	868.07	0.00	0.73	618.46	1,182.26	1,800.72
Grand Total	647.28	1,324.20	1,423.00	3,163.21	6.13	2.91	2,076.41	4,490.33	6,829.74

* Official ODA database from the Council for the Development of Cambodia (CDC): effective disbursements for year 2020 and donors' forecasts for 2021, 2022 and 2023
**EIB disbursement to Cambodia are not reported to CDC. EIB is a very new partner in Cambodia. Figures were provided by EIB and inserted.

Table 1: Planned ODA disbursements between 2021 - 2023 split across all donors. Source: Cambodia MIP

Joint European Strategy financing to Cambodia 2021 - 2027: USD 1.4 billion

In May 2022, European Partners and Cambodia presented the second Joint European Strategy for Development Cooperation with Cambodia 2021 - 2027. The Joint European Strategy financing 2021 - 2027 totals USD 1.4 billion (EEAS, 2022, p.22).

European partners	Already committed									Indicative new contributions									Grand total	
	BE (3)	CH (1)	CZ (6)	DE	EIB	EU (2)	FR	IE	SE (4)	Sum	CH	CZ	DE	EIB	EU	FR	IE	SE		Sum
Priority area 1 - Supply side of governance	-	2.85	-	6.50	-	34.19	2.61	-	4.50	56.66	7	0	0	0	37	0	0	0	44	94.66
Budget & BoP Support	-	-	-	-	-	18.56	-	-	-	18.56	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	18.56
Economic and Development Policy/Planning	-	-	-	-	-	0.04	-	-	-	0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.04
Legal and Judicial	-	-	-	0.50	-	2.84	1.95	-	-	5.29	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5.29
Local Government Reform	-	2.84	-	6.00	-	0.24	-	-	-	9.08	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.08
Other	-	0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.01
Public Financial Management	-	-	-	-	-	12.51	1.56	-	4.50	18.58	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	18.58
Priority area 2 - Demand side of governance	-	-	-	-	-	1.34	-	-	19.70	21.04	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	50	57	78.04
Civil Society	-	-	-	-	-	0.31	-	-	8.60	8.91	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.91
Gender	-	-	-	-	-	0.48	-	-	1.00	1.48	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.48
Human Rights	-	-	-	-	-	0.55	-	-	10.10	10.65	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10.65
Priority area 3 - Human development	12.58	14.12	4.76	105.00	181.49	56.04	191.29	0.10	1.20	566.58	19.9	2.59	0	0	48	0	0	0	70.49	637.07
Community Development	-	0.02	-	-	-	1.54	-	-	-	1.56	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.56
Education (incl TVET)	6.92	9.11	2.99	25.00	-	40.26	0.61	-	1.20	84.69	4.7	1.71	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.41	91.10
Emergency & Food Aid	-	0.93	-	18.30	-	-	-	-	-	19.23	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	19.23
Health	2.44	3.97	1.33	24.00	-	-	0.85	0.10	-	32.69	15.2	0.64	-	-	-	-	-	-	15.84	48.53
Other	-	-	-	2.70	-	0.36	-	-	-	3.06	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.06
Social Protection	4.22	0.08	-	35.00	-	7.78	-	-	-	47.09	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	47.09
Urban Planning & Management	-	-	-	-	-	0.26	20.63	-	-	20.89	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	20.89
Water and Sanitation	-	-	0.84	-	181.49	5.84	169.21	-	-	357.38	0.24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	357.62
Priority area 4 - Trade and private sector development	-	0.48	-	10.52	65.25	4.98	1.64	-	-	82.87	0	0	0	0	62	0	0	0	62	144.87
Business & Financial Services	-	0.01	-	-	-	0.25	0.26	-	-	0.52	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.52
Industrialisation & Trade	-	-	-	10.52	-	4.37	-	-	-	14.89	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	14.89
Technology, Information and Communications	-	-	-	-	-	0.36	-	-	-	0.36	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.36
Tourism	-	0.47	-	-	-	-	0.92	-	-	1.39	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.39
Transportation	-	-	-	-	65.25	-	0.46	-	-	65.71	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	65.71
Priority area 5 - Green Deal	6.49	6.53	0.84	17.00	-	83.83	339.82	0.52	3.50	458.52	7.4	0.6	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	466.52
Agriculture	1.80	6.52	0.46	-	-	56.91	201.45	-	-	267.74	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.2	267.94
Climate Change	-	-	0.16	15.00	-	3.96	25.78	-	-	44.90	5.2	0.32	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	50.42
Energy, Power & Electricity	-	-	0.22	-	-	4.48	72.52	-	-	77.23	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	77.51
Environment and Sustainability	2.81	0.01	-	-	-	4.96	18.13	-	3.50	30.39	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	30.39
Rural Development	1.88	-	-	2.00	-	13.53	20.93	0.52	-	38.65	2.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	41.05
Priority area 6 - Cultural heritage	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.18	-	-	1.18	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.48
Culture, Arts & Sports	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.18	-	-	1.18	0.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.48
Other	-	-	-	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	1.00	1	-	-	-	8	-	-	-	-	9
Grand Total	19.07	23.98	5.60	140.02	246.74	180.37	536.54	0.62	28.90	1,181.84	42.6	3.19	0	0	155	0	0	50	250.79	1,432.63

Table 2: Joint European Strategy Indicative Financing 2021-2027. Source: JES Cambodia total investment 2019 - 2023: USD 59.9 billion

The Cambodia National Strategic Development Plan (NSDP) 2019 - 2023 estimates that approximately USD 59.9 billion is needed in capital investments both from domestic and foreign finance to achieve the growth targets in this period (Kingdom of Cambodia, 2019b, p.223).

Source of Finance	2019p	2020p	2021p	2022p	2023p	Total
(In Million USD)						
Total Public Investment	2,257	3,382	3,376	3,527	3,912	16,454
Domestic finance	738	1,636	1,519	1,539	1,566	7,000
Foreign finance	1,298	1,476	1,561	1,634	1,974	8,154
Total Private Investment	6,519	7,447	8,524	9,774	11,174	43,438
Domestic finance	2,853	3,118	3,405	3,719	4,012	17,107
Foreign finance	3,666	4,328	5,119	6,055	7,162	26,331
Total Investment	8,776	10,830	11,901	13,301	15,086	59,890
(In Billion Riels)						
Total Public Investment	9,257	13,870	13,845	14,463	16,043	67,479
Domestic finance	3,028	6,711	6,230	6,310	6,421	28,700
Foreign finance	5,324	6,053	6,404	6,738	8,096	32,615
Total Private Investment	26,727	30,532	34,950	40,073	45,812	178,096
Domestic finance	11,697	12,786	13,960	15,246	16,447	70,138
Foreign finance	15,029	17,746	20,990	24,826	29,364	107,957
Total Investment	35,984	44,402	48,795	54,536	61,855	245,574

Source: MEF

Note: Exchange rate 1 USD=4,100 Riels, (*) Gap of the total is the RGC's loan payment

Table 3: Capital investment required to achieve Cambodia's Growth Targets 2019 - 2023. Source: NSDP 2019-2023

The table below indicates the allocation of capital investments in the NSDP 2019-2023 by sectors and sub-sectors (Kingdom of Cambodia, 2019b, p.229).

Sectors and Sub-sectors	% of Total	Allocation for 2019-2023	
		Riels (billions)	USD (millions)
Social Sectors	32	30.8	7.5
Education	10	9.6	2.3
Technical and Vocational Training	8	7.8	1.8
Health	10	9.6	2.4
Social Protection/Poverty Reduction	4	3.8	1.0
Economic Sectors	24	23.0	5.6
Agriculture and Land Management	4	3.8	1.0
Seasonal Crops: Rice & others	4	3.8	1.0
Rural Development	12	11.6	2.7
Manufacturing, Mining and Trade	4	3.8	1.0
Infrastructure	21	20.2	5.0
Transportation (Roads, Ports, Railways., Civil Aviation)	12	11.6	2.7
Water and Sanitation (excluding rural)	4	3.8	1.0
Power and Electricity	4	3.8	1.0
Post and Telecommunications	1	1.0	0.2
Services & Cross Sectoral Programs	21	20.2	5.0
Gender Mainstreaming	1.5	1.4	0.4
Tourism	2	2.0	0.5
Environment and Conservation	4	3.8	1.0
Community and Social Services	4	3.8	1.0
Culture and Arts	1.5	1.4	0.4
Governance and Administration	8	7.8	1.8
Unallocated	2	2.0	0.5
Grand Total	100	96.4	23.5

Table 4: Allocation by Sector and Sub-sector of Public Investment in the NSDP 2019-2023.
Source: NSDP 2019-2023

2. Situation of the Sector

2.1 SWOT analysis

This is SWOT analysis which includes the 5 priority areas (energy, skills, labour, gender and market access).

2.1.1 Strengths

Energy - there is a slightly consistent supply of electricity in the GTF sector, though this is improved in clusters of Special Economic Zones (SEZ) and there are energy investments in place. Relatively high but decreasing share of renewable energy in the electricity fuel mix, although, there are plans to move away from coal towards reduced carbon intensive fossil fuels such as gas. Cambodia has established a strategic plan to reduce electricity tariffs for industrial and commercial use: reducing price to USD 0.165 /kWh in Phnom Penh, Kandal and Kampong Speu; setting differential pricing for daytime and night time; expanded coverage to all targeted industrial zones; reducing outages to no more than 12 times or 24 hours per annum (Kingdom of Cambodia, 2015, p.30).

Skills - TVET and Education strategy as well as industry are in talks to create more responsive pathways. Good ASEAN framework being developed with support of EU (EU

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